

Impact of Digital Technology and Fair Use on Intellectual Property Right of Indigenous Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

We are living in an information age ruled by information and communication technology (ICT) whose influx and methodology of communication have changed the way information and by extension knowledge is accessed. These digital technology transformations as discovered are having an effect on cultural knowledge and communication as well as creating new challenges for Indigenous communities more so in the area of traditional or indigenous knowledge. This study therefore is a survey of impact of digital technology and fair use on intellectual property right of indigenous knowledge as Assessed by Librarians. The study was guided by three research questions and adopted a descriptive survey design. The sampled population of the study was 500 librarians purposively selected with the aid of 2023 Librarians Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) certified librarians list, while a Likert type four point structured questionnaire was the principle instrument used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts from the department of measurement and evaluation of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria using Cronbach's alpha. Result showed coefficient of $\alpha=.79$. The questionnaires were sent through respondents emails and were also returned through the same channel 100%. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies, simple percentile as well as mean and presented in tables. The result of the study shows that there are set out intellectual property rights that indigenous knowledge should enjoy which include among others the right to benefit commercially and that digital technologies have made great impact on indigenous knowledge in that digital technologies are helping indigenous groups record and share their traditional knowledge with other Indigenous groups, the wider world and future generations, bringing a wider awareness of their culture to the world as well as bringing awareness of their issues to a wider audience and connecting with other indigenous groups around the world. It was also discovered that digital technology and principle of fair use have adverse effect on the intellectual property right of indigenous knowledge as with it, the indigenous cultural identity may be misrepresented, traditional rulers ignorantly may sell indigenous knowledge without due consideration for the long-term implication of this on their communities and that with digital technology indigenous are exploited of their knowledge on principle of fair use. Based on the findings it was recommended inter-alia that there should be global legislations to cover all possible scenarios to avoid infringing into ones right including the aborigines that own traditional knowledge in that reproducing indigenous work without the custodians' knowledge, especially as it relates to commercial content producers who now makes use of protection software encryptions, licensing and so on to protect the copyright of their materials.

Key words: Intellectual property Right, Digital era, Indigenous knowledge, Intellectual property protection, Copyright, and Digital Technology, Librarian, Information and Communication Technology

Library of Congress Classification No: Z551-656

1. INTRODUCTION

As asserted by Ginsburg (2008) so far the term is disputed, many people consider us to believing in the digital Age. No matter the angle it is looked at, one thing is clear is that we are living in an information age ruled by information and communication technology (ICT) whose influx and

methodology of communication have changed the way information and by extension knowledge is accessed. These digital technology transformations as discovered are having an effect on cultural knowledge and communication as well as creating new challenges for Indigenous communities more so in the area of traditional or indigenous knowledge. Traditional knowledge also called Indigenous knowledge or `native ways of knowing, is a term used to describe the world view of indigenous groups. It is highly linked to location and reflects the way the people see themselves in relation to their environment (Semali, & Kincheloe, 1999) and emanates from the interactions of the social and physical environment as created by a specific geographic area (Viergever, 1999). To this end, UNESCO (2021) defines it as the understandings, skills and philosophies developed by societies with long histories of interaction with their natural surroundings. For rural and indigenous peoples, local knowledge informs decision-making about fundamental aspects of day-to-day life. This knowledge it is added is integral to a cultural complex that also encompasses language, systems of classification, resource use practices, social interactions, ritual and spirituality.

As asserted by Asuquo and Okpa (2023), Indigenous knowledge is the traditional knowledge of the natives of a given geographical area. It is evident in the culture of the indigenes of a particular community. Suffice it to say that it is the knowledge that a local community accumulates over generations of living in a particular environment. This knowledge includes technologies, know-how, skills, practices and beliefs that enable a community to achieve a stable and sustainable livelihood. It is therefore is a native group of activities that cover a wider range of aspects like language, norms, behaviors, farming and healthcare systems held by indigents for survival which is passed from generation to generation. This concept is also used in reference to the large body of knowledge and skills developed outside formal education. Such body of knowledge and skills is rooted in culture and unique to a particular people. It shaped decision making in all domains of life including food habits, health, education, child rearing, natural resource management, and agriculture among others. Suffice it to say, that indigenous knowledge is a set of perceptions, information, and practices that guide local community members in terms of how to best use their local resources, both environmental and cultural.

The argument is that the emergence of ICT has both good and ugly effect on traditional knowledge as it relates to intellectual property protection right and the principle of fair use therefore consideration should be given to how these technologies are used to maximize the benefits and lessen the negative side effects. As noted while some digital technologies are helping Aboriginal groups record and share their traditional knowledge with other Aboriginal groups, the wider world and future generations, new challenges are presented to Aboriginal cultural identity, these emerging technologies also provide new ways to protect traditional Aboriginal knowledge and heritage as well as infringe on their knowledge rights (Steeves, 2015).

According to World Trade Organization (2024) intellectual property rights are the rights given to persons over the creations of their minds which usually give the creator an exclusive right over the use of his/her creation for a certain period of time. It was further explained that Intellectual property

rights are customarily divided into two main areas which are **Copyright and rights related to copyright which involves** the rights of authors of literary and artistic works (such as books and other writings, musical compositions, paintings, sculpture, computer programs and films) are protected by copyright, for a minimum period of 50 years after the death of the author. Also protected through copyright and related rights are the rights of performers (e.g. actors, singers and musicians), producers of phonograms (sound recordings) and broadcasting organizations. The main social purpose of protection of copyright and related rights is to encourage and reward creative work and **industrial property which include among others** protection of distinctive signs, in particular trademarks (which distinguish the goods or services of one undertaking from those of other undertakings) and geographical indications (which identify a good as originating in a place where a given characteristic of the good is essentially attributable to its geographical origin and protection primarily to stimulate innovation, design and the creation of technology.

On the other hand explained Copyright Alliance (2024), principle of fair use is an affirmative defense that can be raised in response to claims by a copyright owner that a person is infringing a copyright. This implies that the principle of fair use permits a party to use a copyrighted work without the copyright owner's permission for purposes such as criticism, comment, news reporting, teaching, scholarship, or research. These purposes only illustrate what might be considered as fair use and are not examples of what will always be considered as fair use. In fact, there are no bright-line rules in determining fair use, since it is determined on a case-by-case basis. But copyright law does establish four factors that must be considered in deciding whether a use constitutes a fair use. These factors are: the purpose and character of the use, including whether such use is of a commercial nature or is for non-profit educational purposes; the nature of the copyrighted work; the amount and substantiality of the portion used in relation to the copyrighted work as a whole; and the effect of the use upon the potential market for or value of the copyrighted work (US Copyright Office, 2022)..

Be that as it may, it is more or less a golden rule that one should give honour to who it is due while the holy Bible puts it in a subtle way when in First Timothy 5:18 admonishes that: "The laborer is worthy of his wages." Deuteronomy 24:15 specifies a periodicity for wage payment: "You shall give him his wages on the day that he earns them before the sun sets, for he is poor and is counting on it, so that he does not cry out to the Lord against you, and it becomes a sin for you. In the intellectual world, an owner of an intellectual property has right over his or her property and an infringement tantamount to crime. As the world of literary works increases individual, institution as well as organizations are faced with all manners of protection of intellectual property right use especially in managing digital environment that has to do with using technology to which many people in the world now have access to. With issues of copyright being unclear in the digital ecosystem, developing or creating copyright of indigenous and cultural heritage in the digital environment globally seems to have become an uphill task.

In this regard, librarians are by training information managers and custodians of knowledge. In which case, they are as a matter of ethics supposed to guide against infringement of copyright. Copyright is a legal right given to an author to his intellectual work in which case no one copies such work without due authorization of the author or publisher as the case may be. In the absence of that, it behooves any one copying the work more so for academic purposes to acknowledge the source through referencing. As explained by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) when a person creates a literary; musical, scientific or artistic work, he or she is the owner of that work and is free to decide on its use. The person (called creator or the author or owner. Of right) can control the destiny of the work. Copyright therefore is the Legal protection extended to the owner of the right in an original Work that he has created. It comprises of two main sets of right the economic right and the moral right (WIPO, 2003). This means that the work is the person's intellectual property that requires to be protected as not to be denied the financial and intellectual recognition gains.

It is against this backdrop that this study becomes imperative as to ascertaining librarians perceived impact of digital technologies and the principle of fair use on intellectual property rights of indigenous knowledge as professionals. The main objectives of this study therefore are to:

1. Identify librarians' perceived intellectual property rights for indigenous knowledge,
2. Ascertain librarians' perceived impact of digital technology on indigenous knowledge and
3. Identify librarians perceived adverse effects of digital technology and principle of fair use on intellectual property rights of IK

1.2. Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What are librarians' perceived intellectual property rights for Indigenous Knowledge?
2. What impact do librarians perceived digital technology has on indigenous knowledge?
3. What are librarians perceived adverse effects of digital technology on intellectual property rights and principle of fair use on Indigenous Knowledge?

2. Literature Review

Being factual, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have remarkably transformed intellectual property rights as they have affected many other things as development of computers and communication technologies allows a faster and effective processing, storage and accessing of information. All said and done, the first concern of copyright in the digital world was raised in the USA subsequent to the Information Infrastructure Task Force (IITF) formation by one-time president of America (President Clinton). Infrastructure Task Force was tasked with articulating the administration's vision of a National Information Infrastructure (NII). This issue became the mandate of the working group on intellectual property rights. The working group considered that a Conference on Fair Use in the digital era (CONFU), bringing together copyright holders and educationist and interested was required to try and develop guidelines for fair use in the digital era. The working group met many times and developed guidelines, although they failed to reach consensus on the

applicability of these guidelines. In the absence of anything else guiding fair use in the digital environment in many institutions and universities especially in the USA, have adopted the guidelines. These guidelines refer to a number of circumstances when digital copying might need to be carried out. For instance, it covers the digitization of images for use in teaching and scholarly work (The White House, 1993). It is permissible for education to digitize analogue images as long as they use thumbnail sketches of those images. Educators may also use images for teaching and scholarly presentations but would be required to seek permission if they were to be published (Association of Research Libraries, 2002).

On the other hand, Intellectual property (IP) refers to creations of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce. IP is protected in law by, for example, patents, copyright and trademarks, which enable people to earn recognition or financial benefit from what they invent or create. By striking the right balance between the interests of innovators and the wider public interest, the IP system aims to foster an environment in which creativity and innovation can flourish (WIPO, 2023). While intellectual property protection is generally seen as ambiguous as it ironically applies to everyday activities that people do for instance photocopying of documents, recording music's for their personal use, literary works of authors, writers, illustrators, editors, and actors among others (Litmus, 2000). There is the belief that many people are unaware of what intellectual property protection entails and means to both the creators and users of knowledge. In this regard, Kari, Ogar & Oyeniran (2014) affirmed in their study that intellectual property protection right is associated with the legislative rights given to an author, editor or any individual or institution responsible for the creation of original literary works as to prevent any likely abuse of use. The implication is that intellectual property rights are meant to reward, recognize and encourage innovation and creativity as well as bestow upon the recipients the right to contest against anyone who infringes on their rights.

According to World Trade Organization (2024) intellectual property rights are the rights given to persons over the creations of their minds which usually give the creator an exclusive right over the use of his/her creation for a certain period of time. It was further explained that Intellectual property rights are customarily divided into two main areas which are **Copyright and rights related to copyright which involves** the rights of authors of literary and artistic works (such as books and other writings, musical compositions, paintings, sculpture, computer programs and films) are protected by copyright, for a minimum period of 50 years after the death of the author. Also protected through copyright and related (sometimes referred to as "neighboring") rights are the rights of performers (e.g. actors, singers and musicians), producers of phonograms (sound recordings) and broadcasting organizations. The main social purpose of protection of copyright and related rights is to encourage and reward creative work and **industrial property which include among others** protection of distinctive signs, in particular trademarks (which distinguish the goods or services of one undertaking from those of other undertakings) and geographical indications (which identify a good as originating in a place where a given characteristic of the good is essentially attributable to its geographical origin and protection primarily to stimulate innovation, design and the creation of technology. In this

category, fall inventions protected by patents, industrial designs and trade secrets. The protection is usually given for a finite term, typically 20 years in the case of patents.

Copyright, or authors' right, is a legal term used to describe the rights that creators have in their literary, artistic and scientific works. Copyright serves the public interest by helping to ensure that creators can earn a fair reward for their work, thus encouraging further creative endeavor, and by making sure that works are properly acknowledged and respected (World Intellectual Property Organization, 2020). Be that as it may, there are different national laws on copyright in different territories, as with other form of intellectual property, however international law establishes certain minimum standards of protection. Ultimately, copyright arises as soon as a work is created as there is no need for a creator to register a work or complete any other formalities in order to gain protection inasmuch as some countries do operate voluntary copyright registration schemes. All the same, countries are required to protect most copyrighted works throughout the life of the creator and for at least 50 years after the creator's death (WIPO, 2020).

In same vein, Anaeme (2014) describes intellectual copyright as an intangible right protecting the products of human intelligence and creation. It's therefore defined as the legal rights granted to authors or writers for their creative and original literary, dramatic or musical works as the exclusive right to do or authorize other persons to do certain acts in relation to the work. As revealed by World Intellectual Property Organization (2003) document on intellectual property encompasses when a person creates a literary musical, scientific or artistic work, he or she is the owner and is free to decide on its use as the creator the author or owner of right and can control the destiny of the work. The organization went ahead and defined copyright is the legal protection extended to the owner of the right in an original work that he has created and comprises of two main sets of right, the economic right and the moral right. Protecting the right of creators and authors encourages them to continue contributing to knowledge. To this end noted Mears (2003) the purpose of copy right is to promote the progress of science and useful arts and to encourage others to build freely upon the ideas and information conveyed in a work. With this, authors are encouraged to produce more knowledge by being given the rights to benefits commercially and otherwise from their work. It is pertinent to state that the main international agreement on intellectual copyright is the Berne Convention of 1886, administered by World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), to which most countries have fashioned their own copyright laws.

As the world bask in euphoria of exponential growth in information masterminded by ICT, powered by computers and taken to unimaginable height by the internet individuals, institutions as well as organizations are faced with all challenges of protecting intellectual property right use especially in managing digital environment that has to do with using technology that is almost accessible to all globally. With the uncertainty hovering around copyright in the digital ecosystem, developing or creating copyright of indigenous knowledge and cultural heritage in the global digital ecosystem has remained an illusion. Traditional knowledge provides a different viewpoint of the world and a different method of interacting with it (Semali, & Kincheloe, 1999) as it is connected to the cultural heritage of

an Indigenous group and often integrated into cultural practices (Simeone, 2004). Traditional knowledge is important to the communities from which such knowledge originated as it is the basis for everyday living and the health and welfare of the community. It is becoming more prominent in western interests because of the emphasis on sustainability, especially in the fields of medicine, commercially valuable biodiversity, or conservation of biodiversity (Viergever, 1999). Policy makers are now using traditional knowledge to help inform them in a variety of areas, and efforts are being made to not only promote but also protect indigenous knowledge from appropriation (Simeone, 2004).

Indigenous knowledge (IK) as a systematic body of knowledge acquired by local people through the accumulation of experiences, informal experiments and understanding of the environment in a given culture arises from life experiences and which is passed down from generation through word of mouth in the form of idioms, proverbs, folklore, songs, rites of passage and rituals. Indigenous knowledge is home-grown knowledge that enables communities to make sense of who they are and to interact with their environment in ways that sustain life. While knowledge is generally described as being explicit or tacit; Indigenous knowledge is mainly tacit as it resides in people`s heads and as to most parts not been codified (Inf Scipedia, 2024).

There has been recognition of the economic potential of indigenous knowledge over the past few years, and this has brought issues of intellectual rights of indigenous knowledge to the fore. It is very clear that IK has contributed immensely to some medicinal and cosmetic products in use today but it was not until 1992 that the importance of IK was recognized and the Conventions of Biological Diversity (CBD) was put in place. There is however a contradiction between intellectual property and indigenous knowledge. Intellectual property, according to Blankeney (1997) represents propitiation of traditional knowledge and by definition traditional knowledge is not individual property. IK is generally perceived to be a collective property and is owned by communities. However, such communities are usually not able to take control of this knowledge and this often becomes the responsibility of custodians such as chiefs. It has historically been the case that these chiefs have “sold” indigenous knowledge without due consideration for the long-term implication of this on their communities.

Patenting is a way of protecting intellectual property that goes some ways in assigning intellectual property right. As shared the granting of patent for the Hoodia Cactus to the San commonly in South Africa (Mutula, 2002). The problem though for most other communities is that they have limited legal know-how, Savvy and means to engage agents of multi-nationals who appropriate their IK for their own gain where they can negotiate for their right, the struggle has been protracted. The experience of the San people in securing recognition of ownership and a share of the profits from the Hoodia Cactus patent is a case in point that illustrates the difficulties that communities have in claiming their right.

The record shows that the negotiation took three years with San sued South African council for scientific and industrial research. The question is how many communities will have the wherewithal and tenacity to engage an organization as big as the national research council. However, because IK is not documented, there is a danger that it would disappear or die off as people stepped in the ways and knowledge of communities. This is very real danger because as more people become educated,

they come into conclusion that only knowledge that has been through the rigor of scientific, laboratory experimentation as real knowledge. They tend to view IK as inferior and based on hunches and superstitions. There is therefore a need to preserve this information and knowledge as it is in fact valuable to the society. Preserving it however, means documenting it and once a work is documented in a fixed format, it is automatically copyrighted. The question is who owns the copyright? Is it the community from which it was obtained or is it the individual or organization that took the responsibility to document the knowledge? Ideally, the community should have the controlling right, but practically, this has not always been the case. In so many occasions historians and anthropologists have studied communities and recorded their culture, traditions, ways of life and indigenous knowledge, and have claimed the credit.

A case in point is the famous Oladunwo Egungun bi-annual cultural festival celebrated by the Okemesi community in Ekiti state, Nigeria that enjoys so much patronage from multi-nationals, Nigerian Television Authority (NTA), Mobile Telecommunication Network (MTN), and other mobile networks as well as many other organizations all over the world has become a such of concern and worry to all the members of the community as most of these organizations and multinationals come to watch and record the cultural activities and appropriate the indigenous knowledge for their own gain. In most cases they hardly acknowledge the community role and the people involved (DOCF, 2021).

Indigenous knowledge property rights are generally part of intellectual property known as industrial property. However, the IK property rights are still very much under discussion locally and internationally. Even the world intellectual property organization has not yet been able to promulgate the regulation of intellectual property for traditional or IK holders. However, some progress has been made with the establishment of working bodies within WIPO to establish procedures of protecting traditional IK. The Berne convention on copyright and the agreement on Trade Related aspects of Intellectual Property Right (TRIPR) and some agreement that attempt to protect indigenous knowledge from theft and piracy (WIPO, 2003).

Furtherance, there have been a number of activities and initiatives aimed at digitizing and captioning African IK. One of which is the world Bank IK programming which maintains a data base of IK, where people and communities can contribute IK. While this may be a positive development that enables people who would not otherwise know or come to appreciate other`s people culture to do so, it also poses a number of moral questions (Britz & Lor, 2003). One of the challenges identified Britz and Lor was that the originating communities will not be identified as the original creators of their cultural heritage and will therefore not have the right to control access and non-disclosure of certain categories of their cultural heritage for instance, the artifact. Up till now the traditional knowledge are folklore set up in 2000 and the WIPO Intergovernmental Committee on Intellectual Property as Genetic Resources, does not have the answers to these questions (WIPO, 2003).

However in May 24, 2024, WIPO Member States in Geneva, adopted a historic New Treaty on Intellectual Property, Genetic Resources and Associated Traditional Knowledge in which member states approved a groundbreaking new Treaty related to intellectual property (IP), genetic resources

and associated traditional knowledge, marking a historic breakthrough that capped decades of negotiations. As asserted it is not just the first new WIPO Treaty in over a decade but also the first one that deals with genetic resources and traditional knowledge held by Indigenous Peoples as well as local communities. Through this declared Tang (2024), we are showing that the IP system can continue to incentivize innovation while evolving in a more inclusive way, responding to the needs of all countries and their communities adding that this agreement by consensus is not just the culmination of a 25 year negotiating journey, but also a strong signal that multilateralism is alive and well at WIPO. So far, the Final Act is also open for signature after adoption which implies that there is still no bidding Act for now.

On the need for intellectual property right for indigenous knowledge it was highlighted to include among others; the right to benefit commercially, the right to prevent and control commercial use of the knowledge, the right to own and control one`s own knowledge, the right to be acknowledged and attributed to the knowledge and the right to prevent offensive and fallacious use of the knowledge

Indigenous knowledge generally belongs to communities, and once such knowledge is digitized, then one may wonder whether the communities from which it originates will have right to it and if so, what sort of rights, given the general powerlessness of communities against multinationals. Will they able to exercise the rights outlined above? History has shown otherwise. Communities have been unable to control their rights once their knowledge has been codified or digitized: they have been powerless to prevent their knowledge from been commercialized and used in derogatory ways which against the interest of the communities. Consequently, Britz and Lor (2003) proposed a few numbers of basic principles that should assist in the digitization of indigenous knowledge in this digital era. Among which is the writer view that digitization should not lead to trivialization of the culture where it is used offensively and for enriching other people other than the community who own the knowledge. Indigenous knowledge owners should maintain their ownership rights. Above all, the IK ownership should not fall into the hands of those digitizing it but have no say in what should or should not be digitized.

When it comes to benefits, it has been noted that digital resources, have positively affected indigenous knowledge. In that technologies enhance communications as they allow people that are widely distributed to communicate with each other easily and efficiently. Many Indigenous groups have also been successful in using digital technology to bring a wider awareness of their culture to the world (Ginsburg, 2008). By using mainstream communication methods they can bring awareness of their issues to a wider audience, as well as connecting with other indigenous groups around the world (Coombe, 2000). When used correctly, with Indigenous groups in control of the production, technology can help to increase cultural activism by enabling indigenous groups to take control of how their culture is portrayed and how their message is spread to national and international forums (Ginsburg, 2008). Digital technologies can be a cost efficient way to create and publish information and allowing individual and community ownership over digital productions. Additionally, if desired, certain aspects of a website can be made private to community members only, while allowing public access to selected sections (Coombe, 2000). For knowledge that we could consider to be part of the

physical sciences, digital data bases are being compiled to keep a record of information such as the biodiversity in a particular area (Coombe, 2000).

One challenge in using digital resources to preserve knowledge is digital technology itself. The choice of technology is very important and must fulfill many criteria. It should be easily affordable and simple to use; but, more importantly, it should be secure and private in order to protect the knowledge and the rights of the indigenous group (Hunter, 2006). Many rural communities also have unreliable access to electricity which can be more problematic for some technologies than others (Ginsburg, 2008). In some cases the technology is used to preserve knowledge within the community and is not intended for a wider distribution (Hunter, 2006). Additionally, consideration should also be given to the type of technology used and its longevity (Ngulube, 2002). There are also important cultural challenges presented by digital technologies. The use of digital technologies may also challenge traditional thoughts on ownership of knowledge, and this can result in a loss of stewardship by indigenous communities who are publishing content on the Internet (Ginsburg, 2008). While the Internet is also culturally biased in favour of western culture, this should not prevent people of First Nations heritage from accessing and producing internet media. Instead it should help them make informed decisions about how to use digital technologies in their best interests (Howe, 1998).

3. Methodology

The study is a survey type that was guided by three research questions coined in line with the research objectives therefore adopted a descriptive survey design. The sampled population of the study is 500 librarians purposively selected from universities in Nigeria covering both public and private with the aid of 2023 Librarians Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) certified librarians list, while a Likert type four point structured questionnaire was the principle instrument used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts from the department of measurement and evaluation of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria using Cronbach's alpha. Result showed coefficient of $\alpha=.79$. The questionnaires were sent through respondents emails and were also returned through the same channel 100%. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies, simple percentile as well as mean and presented in tables.

4. Presentation of Data

The data as displayed in table 1 above reveal the intellectual rights for indigenous knowledge. The data did show that 500 respondents representing 100% strongly agree that intellectual property right for indigenous knowledge include the right to be acknowledged and attributed to the knowledge as well as the right to benefit commercially, 90.2% or 451 respondents strongly agree to the right to prevent offensive and fallacious use of indigenous knowledge while over 90% strongly agree or agree that indigenes should enjoy the right to prevent and control commercial use of their indigenous knowledge and the right to own and control their own knowledge.

Research Question 1: What are the intellectual property rights for Indigenous Knowledge?

Table 1: Librarians’ perceived intellectual property rights for indigenous knowledge

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
The right to benefit commercially	500	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
The right to prevent and control commercial use of the knowledge	432	86.4	12	2.4	23	4.6	33	6.6	3.67
The right to own and control one’s own knowledge,	444	88.8	42	8.4	***	***	14	2.8	3.83
The right to be acknowledged and attributed to the knowledge	500	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
The right to prevent offensive and fallacious use of the knowledge	451	90.2	49	9.8	***	***	***	***	3.90

Research Question 2: What impact do librarians perceived that digital technology has on indigenous knowledge?

Table 2: Librarians’ perceived impact of digital technology on indigenous knowledge

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Digital technologies are helping Indigenous groups record and share their traditional knowledge with other Indigenous groups, the wider world and future generations	500	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Digital technology provides new ways to protect traditional indigenous knowledge and heritage	120	24	36	7.2	96	19.2	248	49.6	2.06
Indigenous groups can successfully use digital technology to bring a wider awareness of their culture to the world	500	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
By using mainstream communication methods Indigenous can bring awareness of their issues to a wider audience as well as connecting with other indigenous groups around the world	500	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
When used correctly, with Indigenous groups in control of the production, technology can help to increase cultural activism by enabling indigenous groups to take control of how their culture is portrayed and how their message is spread to national and international forums	213	42.6	147	29.4	133	26.6	7	1.4	3.13

Table 2 above contains data on the impact of digital technology on indigenous knowledge. The data indicate that 100% or 500 respondents strongly agree that digital technologies are helping Indigenous groups record and share their traditional knowledge with other Indigenous groups, the wider world and future generations, bring a wider awareness of their culture to the world as well as bring awareness of their issues to a wider audience and connecting with other indigenous groups around

the world but with a mean (X) of 2.06 it was strongly disagreed that digital technology provides new ways to protect traditional indigenous knowledge and heritage as 344 respondents representing 68.8% indicated so while 156 or 31.2% thought otherwise.

Research Question 3: What are librarians perceived adverse effects of digital technology on intellectual property rights and principle of fair use on Indigenous Knowledge?

Table 3: Librarians perceived Adverse effect of digital technology and principle of fair use on intellectual property rights of IK

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Digital technology infringes on indigenous knowledge rights	390	78	110	22	***	***	***	***	3.78
Indigenous cultural identity may be misrepresented	500	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
Digital technology is not secured and private in as to ensure protection of the knowledge and the rights of the indigenous group	230	46	176	35.2	66	13.2	28	5.6	3.22
The use of digital technologies may also challenge traditional thoughts on ownership of knowledge and this may result in a loss of stewardship by indigenous communities who are publishing content on the Internet	300	60	87	17.4	54	10.8	59	11.8	3.26
Traditional rulers ignorantly may sell indigenous knowledge without due consideration for the long-term implication of this on their communities	500	100	***	***	***	***	***	***	4.00
With digital technology indigenous are exploited of their knowledge on principle of fair use	500	100	***	***	***	***	**	***	4.00

Table 3 shows that data collected in respect of the librarians perceived effect of digital technology and principle of fair use on intellectual property rights of Indigenous Knowledge. The data indicate that all the 500 respondents or 100% strongly agree that digital technology and principle of fair use have adverse effect on the intellectual property right of indigenous knowledge as with it, the Indigenous cultural identity may be misrepresented, traditional rulers ignorantly may sell indigenous knowledge without due consideration for the long-term implication of this on their communities and that with digital technology indigenous are exploited of their knowledge on principle of fair use while over 70% strongly agree or agree that digital technology is not secured and private in as to ensure protection of the knowledge and the rights of the indigenous group and that the use of digital technologies may also challenge traditional thoughts on ownership of knowledge and this may result in a loss of stewardship by indigenous communities who are publishing content on the Internet.

5. Discussion of Findings

The outcome of this study as shown in table 1 revealed that there are set out intellectual property rights that indigenous knowledge should enjoy. These rights as discovered include, The right to

benefit commercially, The right of indigenous to prevent and control commercial use of the knowledge, The right to own and control one`s own knowledge, the right to be acknowledged and attributed to the knowledge and the right by indigenous to prevent offensive and fallacious use of the knowledge. This result is quite contrary to the narratives as expressed by Britz and Lor (2003) that history has shown otherwise as communities have been unable to control their rights once their knowledge has been codified or digitized: they have been powerless to prevent their knowledge from been commercialized and used in derogatory ways which is against the interest of the communities. So this heartening they noted is that the originating communities will not be identified as the original creators of their cultural heritage and will therefore not have the right to control access and non-disclosure of certain categories of their cultural heritage for instance, the artifact and that up till now the traditional knowledge folklore set up in 2000 and the WIPO Intergovernmental Committee on Intellectual Property as Genetic Resources, does not have the answers to these questions (WIPO, 2003) though the Geneva 2024 Treaty if adopted and signed as an Act may put an end to it all (WIPO, 2024).

The study also found out that digital technologies have made great impact on indigenous knowledge in that digital technologies are helping Indigenous groups record and share their traditional knowledge with other Indigenous groups, the wider world and future generations, bringing a wider awareness of their culture to the world as well as bringing awareness of their issues to a wider audience and connecting with other indigenous groups around the world among other benefits (see table 2). This finding is in tandem with the assertion of Ginsburg (2008) that technologies enhance communications as they allow people that are widely distributed to communicate with each other easily and efficiently noting that indigenous groups have also been successful in using digital technology to bring a wider awareness of their culture to the world By using mainstream communication methods they can bring awareness of their issues to a wider audience, as well as connecting with other indigenous groups around the world (Coombe, 2000).

The study further discovered that regardless of the numerous impacts that digital technologies have on intellectual property rights of indigenous knowledge, librarians` perception is that digital technology in conjunction with principle of fair use has notable adverse effect on indigenous knowledge. As revealed by the data collected and analyzed, librarians perceived that digital technology and principle of fair use have adverse effect on the intellectual property right of indigenous knowledge as with it, the indigenous cultural identity may be misrepresented, traditional rulers ignorantly may sell indigenous knowledge without due consideration for the long-term implication of this on their communities and that with digital technology indigenous are exploited of their knowledge on principle of fair use as well as that digital technology is not secured and private in as to ensure protection of the knowledge and the rights of the indigenous group and that the use of digital technologies may also challenge traditional thoughts on ownership of knowledge and this may result in a loss of stewardship by indigenous communities. This discovering collaborate the stand of Ginsburg (2008) who posits that there are important cultural challenges presented by digital technologies in that the use of digital

technologies may also challenge traditional thoughts on ownership of knowledge and this can result in a loss of stewardship by indigenous communities who are publishing content on the Internet.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Going by the findings of this study, librarians' perception is that digital technologies are like double edged sword to indigenous knowledge. Inasmuch as it has created a window of marketing the indigenous culture and knowledge to the wider world, it has at the same time exposed the intellectual property right of indigenous knowledge to debacle in that indigenous may not enjoy the right to prevent and control commercial use of their indigenous knowledge and the right to own and control their own knowledge. Ultimately, the digitization of information and the proliferations of networks as a result of internet remain the major obstacles of copyright and Intellectual property right of indigenous knowledge as they have now moved from being a concern of creators' publishers and writers but now at the very heart of using technology to which many people in the world now have access. With the issue of copyright and intellectual property rights being unclear in the digital environment there is every need therefore, for nations of the world to unite and tackle some of the issues that arise from intellectual property right and the digital environment more so as they concern indigenous knowledge. In the light of the above, the following suggestions are hereby put forward:

1. There should be global legislations to cover all possible scenarios to avoid infringing into one's right including the aborigines that own traditional knowledge in that reproducing indigenous work without the custodians' knowledge, especially as it relates to commercial content producers who now makes use of protection software encryptions, licensing and so on to protect the copyright of their materials. This however, is not really encouraging for under developed countries that lack the resources to acquire access to information. Even though, WIPO through the intergovernmental Committee on Genetic Resources Traditional Knowledge and Folklore is still working out measure to preserve indigenous knowledge,
2. Government and civil society especially those of developing nations should think ways to safe guard the intellectual property of communities that own indigenous knowledge.
3. Countries of the world should come up with indigenous databases that would be used such that the database could check whenever individual is claiming or applying for intellectual property rights.
4. Furthermore, when indigenous knowledge is being digitized, a clear statement of intellectual property rights should be included to show who the owners are and under what condition the Indigenous Knowledge could be used. To this end, there is the need for the cultural and moral rights of owners of Indigenous knowledge to be guided and protected.
5. Finally digitization should not lead to trivialization of the culture where it is used offensively and enriching other people other than the community who owns the indigenous knowledge. The underlying factor is that indigenous knowledge owners should maintain their ownership rights. They should not fall into the hands of those digitizing them as it happened in the past

where those who claimed they were documenting it later went out to commercialize it without the knowledge of the communities.

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